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PROCEEDINGS

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Editors: Monica Pratesi and Cira Pena

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PLENARY SESSIONS

- (A) E. Baldacci [Financial Crises and their Impacts: Data Gaps and Innovation in Statistical Production.](#)
- (B) D. Dunson [Probabilistic inference from big and complex data.](#)
- (C) S. Strozza [Foreign immigration in Italy: a forty-year-old history.](#)

SPECIALIZED SESSION (SPE)

(SPE-01) Inference, sampling and survey design

- P. Conti [Resampling from finite populations under complex designs: the pseudo-population approach.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Andreis, D. Marella, F. Mecatti)
- P. Righi [A joint use of model based and design based frameworks for defining optimal sampling designs.](#) (Co-author(s): P. D. Falorsi)
- A. Ruiz-Gazen [A unified approach for robustness in survey sampling.](#) (Co-author(s): J. Beaumont, D. Haziza)

(SPE-02) Multivariate models for risk assessment

- M. Billio [A Bayesian nonparametric approach to macroeconomic risk.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Casarin, M. Costola, M Guindani)
- P. Cerchiello [Bank risk contagion:an analysis through big data.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Giudici, G. Nicola)
- L. De Angelis [A Markov-switching regression model with non-Gaussian innovations for systemic risk measurement.](#) (Co-author(s): C. Viroli)

(SPE-03) Bayesian nonparametrics

- D. Durante [Bayesian Nonparametric Modeling of Dynamic International Relations.](#) (Co-author(s): D. Dunson)
- A. Guglielmi [Bayesian autoregressive semiparametric models for gap times of recurrent events.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Paulon, M. De Iorio)
- A. Rodriguez [Restricted Nonparametric Mixtures models for Disease Clustering.](#) (Co-author(s): T. Xifara)

(SPE-04) Statistical methods for the analysis of gene-environment interaction in the study of complex pathologies

- C. Angelini** [An introduction to next generation sequencing for studying omic-environment interactions.](#)
- L. Calciano** [Statistical approaches for the evaluation of genetic associations in complex diseases: the heterogeneity of asthma phenotypes.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Portas, S. Accordini)
- Y. Pankaj** [Improved case-only approach to study genome-wide gene-environment interaction.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Freitag-Wolf, A. Dempfle, W. Lieb, M. Krawczak)

(SPE-05) Nonlinear time series

- M. Niglio** [Probabilistic properties of Self Exciting Threshold Autoregressive processes.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Giordano, C. D. Vitale)
- T. Proietti** [Optimal prediction of stochastic trends.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Giovannelli)
- H. Tong** [On model selection from a finite family of possibly misspecified models.](#) (Co-author(s): H. Hsu, C. Ing)

(SPE-06) Spatial analyses in demography

- F. Heins** [Measuring residential segregation with spatial indices: an appraisal and applications for the metropolitan area of Rome.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Benassi, F. Lipizzi, E. Paluzzi)
- A. Mazza** [Immigrants' settlement patterns in the city of Naples.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Gabrielli, S. Strozza)
- L. Natale** [Native Immigration and Pull Factor Evolution in Italy: a Spatial Approach.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Santacroce, F. G. Truglia)

(SPE-07) Recent developments in Volatility modeling

- R. Casarin** [Dynamic Model Averaging for Quantile Regression.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Bernardi, B. Mailet, L. Petrella)
- A. Rahbek** [Testing volatility: consistency of bootstrap testing for a parameter on the boundary of the parameter space.](#)
- E. Ruiz** [Asymmetric Stochastic Volatility Models: Properties and Estimation.](#) (Co-author(s): V. Czellar, X. Mao, H. Veiga)

(SPE-08) Advances in ordinal contingency table analysis

- L. D'Ambra** [Dimensionality reduction methods for contingency tables with ordinal variables.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Amenta, A. D'Ambra)
- R. Lombardo** [Modelling Trends in Ordered Three-Way Non-Symmetrical Correspondence Analysis.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Kroonenberg, E. Beh)
- M. Riani** [Using Collapsing and Multiple Comparisons to Detect Association in Two Way Contingency Tables.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Arsenis)

(SPE-09) Statistical models for directional and circular data

- C. Ley** [The WeiSSVM: a tractable, parsimonious and flexible model for cylindrical data.](#)
- G. Mastrantonio** [The multivariate projected-skew normal distribution: Bayesian estimation and a hidden Markov model application.](#)
- A. Panzera** [Circular density estimation via matching local trigonometric moments.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Di Marzio, S. Fensore, C. C. Taylor)

(SPE-10) The interplay between frequentist and bayesian inference

- C. Grazian** [Classical inference for intractable likelihoods.](#)
- J. Hannig** [Fusion learning for Interlaboratory Comparison.](#) (Co-author(s): Q. Feng, H. Iyer, C. Wang, X. Liu)
- F. Pauli** [p-value in science: a review of issues and proposed solutions.](#)

(SPE-11) Société Française de Statistique

- B.H. Avner** [Stochastic Block Model for Multiplex network: an application to a multilevel network of researchers..](#)
- Y. Bennani** [Nonnegative Matrix Factorization for Transfer Learning.](#) (Co-author(s): I. Redko)
- T. Laloe** [Detection of dependence patterns with delay.](#)
- J. Poggi** [Disaggregated Electricity Forecasting using Wavelet-Based Clustering of Individual Consumers.](#) (Co-author(s): J. Cugliari, Y. Goude)

(SPE-12) National accounts

- A. Coli** [The European Welfare State in times of crisis according to macroeconomic official statistics.](#) (Co-author(s): E. Micheletti, B. Pacini)
- C. Martelli** [National Account and Open Data: a new semantic approach.](#)
- G. Oneto** [New information contents of the National Accounts for the monitoring of the economic situation.](#)

(SPE-13) Statistical tools for monitoring the educational system and assessing students' performances

- L. Grilli** [Evaluation of university students' performance through a multidimensional finite mixture IRT model.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Bacci, F. Bartolucci, C. Rampichini)
- G. Leckie** [Monitoring school performance using value-added and value-table models: Lessons from the UK.](#)
- P. Sarnacchiaro** [A statistical model to assess teacher performance.](#) (Co-author(s): I. Camminatiello, R. Palma)

(SPE-14) Robust inference by bounded estimating functions

- A.C. Monti** [M Estimation based Inference for Ordinal Response Model.](#)
- E. Ruli** [Approximate Robust Bayesian Inference with an Application to Linear Mixed Models.](#) (Co-author(s): N. Sartori, L. Ventura)
- J. Valeinis** [Some robust methods using empirical likelihood for two samples.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Velina, E. Cers, G. Luta)

SOLICITED SESSION (SOL)

(SOL-01) Subjective wellbeing and demographic events over the life course

- G. Fuochi** [Cultural and institutional drivers of basic psychological needs satisfaction.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Conzo, A. Aassve, L. Mencarini)
- L. Mencarini** [Five reasons to be happy about childbearing.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Aassve, F. Luppi)
- B. Nowok** [Migration motivations and migrants' satisfaction in the life course: A sequence analysis of geographical mobility trajectories in the United Kingdom.](#)
- A. Pirralha** [Does becoming a parent change the meaning of happiness and life satisfaction? Evidence from the European Social Survey.](#) (Co-author(s): H. Dobewall)

(SOL-02) Statistics for equitable and sustainable development

- E. di Bella** [Wellbeing and sustainable development: a multi-indicator approach to evaluate urban waste management systems.](#) (Co-author(s): B. Cavalletti, M. Corsi)
- C. Giusti** [Small Area Estimation for Local Welfare Indicators in Italy.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Marchetti, L. Faustini, L. Porciani)
- T. Laureti** [Does socio-economic variables influence the Italians' adherence towards a sustainable diet?.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Secondi)
- F. Riccardini** [Sustainability of wellbeing: an analysis of resilience and vulnerability through subjective indicators.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Bachelet, F. Maggino)

(SOL-03) New approaches to treat undercoverage and nonresponse

- F. Andreis** [Methodological perspectives for surveying rare and clustered population: towards a sequentially adaptive approach.](#)
- E. Furfaro** [Dealing with under-coverage bias via Dual/Multiple Frame designs: a simulation study for telephone surveys.](#)

D. Haziza [Weight adjustment procedures for the treatment of unit nonresponse in surveys.](#) (Co-author(s): É. Lesage)

E. Kabzinska [Empirical likelihood multiplicity adjusted estimator for multiple frame surveys.](#) (Co-author(s): Y. G. Berger)

(SOL-04) Statistical models and methods for network data

M. Cugmas [Measuring stability of co-authorship structures in time.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Ferligoj)

J. Koskinen [A dynamic discrete-choice model for movement flows.](#) (Co-author(s): T. Mueller, T. Grund)

G. Ragozini [Prototyping and Comparing Networks through Archetypal Analysis.](#) (Co-author(s): D. De Stefano, M.R. D'Esposito)

S. Zaccarin [Modeling network dynamics: evidence from policy-driven innovation networks.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Caloffi, D. De Stefano, F. Rossi, M. Russo)

(SOL-05) Recent developments in computational statistics

R. Argiento [A conditional algorithm for Bayesian finite mixture models via normalized point process.](#)

S. Favaro [Thompson sampling for species discovery.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Battiston, Y. Teh)

A. Mira [An application of Reinforced Urn Process to advice network data.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Peluso, P. Muliere, F. Pallotti, A. Loni)

N. Sartori [Bootstrap prepivoting in the presence of many nuisance parameters.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Bellio, I. Kosmidis, A. Salvan)

(SOL-06) Statisticians meet naturalists: issues on ecological and environmental statistics

F. Ferretti [Estimating the abundance of wildlife ungulate populations in Mediterranean areas: methods, problems and findings.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Sforzi)

M. Ferretti [The monitoring of forests in Europe: methods, problems and proposals.](#)

D. Rocchini [The power of generalized entropy for biodiversity assessment by remote sensing: an open source approach.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Delucchi, G. Bacaro)

(SOL-07) From survey data to new data sources and big data in official statistics

G. Barcaroli [Machine learning and statistical inference: the case of Istat survey on ICT.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Bianchi, R. Bruni, A. Nurra, S. Salamone, M. Scarnò)

S. Falorsi [Forecasting Italian Youth Unemployment Rate Using Online Search Data.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Loriga, A. Naccarato, A. Pierini)

B. Liseo [Bayesian nonparametric methods for record linkage.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Tancredi)

T. Tuoto [Exploring solutions for linking Big Data in Official Statistics.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Di Consiglio, D. Fusco)

(SOL-08) Symbolic data analysis methods and applications

E. Diday [Explanatory and discriminatory power of variables in Symbolic Data Analysis.](#)

M.B. Ferraro [Fuzzy and possibilistic approach to clustering of imprecise data.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Giordani)

L. Grassini [Symbolic data analysis approach for monitoring the stability of monuments..](#) (Co-author(s): B. Bertaccini, G. Biagi, A. Giusti)

M. Ichino [Similarity and Dissimilarity Measures for Mixed Feature-type Symbolic Data.](#) (Co-author(s): K. Umbleja)

(SOL-09) Compositional analysis

L. Crosato [Forecasting CPI weights through compositional VARIMA: an application to Italian data..](#) (Co-author(s): F. Lovisolo, B. Zavanella)

J. A. Marín-Fernández [Understanding association rules from a compositional data approach.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Vives-Mestres, R. Kenett)

A. Menafoglio [Object Oriented Geostatistical Simulation of Functional Compositions via Dimensionality Reduction in Bayes spaces.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Guadagnini, P. Secchi)

V. Simonacci [Fitting CANDECOMP-PARAFAC model for compositional data: a combined SWATLD-ALS algorithm.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Di Palma, V. Todorov)

(SOL-10) Sustainable development: theory, measures and applications

F. Riccardini [Measuring sustainable development goals from now to 2030.](#)

F. Riccardini [How the nexus of food/water/energy can be seen with the perspective on well-being of people and the Italian BES framework.](#) (Co-author(s): D. De Rosa)

T. Rondinella [An innovative methodology for the analysis of sustainability, inclusion and smartness of growth through Europe2020 indicators..](#) (Co-author(s): E. Grimaccia)

P. Ungaro [The Italian population behaviours toward environmental sustainability: a study from Istat surveys.](#) (Co-author(s): I. Mingo, V. Talucci)

(SOL-11) Detecting heterogeneity in ordinal data surveys

E. Di Nardo [CUB models: a preliminary Fuzzy approach to heterogeneity.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Simone)

S. Giordano [Modelling uncertainty in bivariate models for ordinal responses.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Colombi, A. Gottard, M. Iannario)

M. Manisera Treatment of “don’t know” responses in rating data: effects on the heterogeneity of the CUB distribution. (Co-author(s): P. Zuccolotto)

F. Pennoni Modelling a multivariate hidden Markov process on survey data.

(SOL-12) Active ageing: age management and lifelong learning strategies

P. E. Cardone Age management in Italian companies. Findings of two Isfol surveys. (Co-author(s): M. Aversa, L. D’Agostino)

A. Lorenti Working after Retirement in Europe.

C. Polli Older low-skilled workers and economic crisis in Italy. (Co-author(s): R. Angotti)

G. Rivellini Population ageing and human resources management. A chance for Applied Demography. (Co-author(s): F. Marcaletti, F. Racioppi)

(SOL-13) Statistical models for evaluating policy impact

M. Bia Evaluation of Training Programs by exploiting secondary outcomes in Principal Stratification frameworks: the case of Luxembourg. (Co-author(s): F. Li, A. Mercatanti)

G. Cerulli Testing Stability of Regression Discontinuity Models. (Co-author(s): Y. Dongz, A. Lewbel, A. Poulsen)

R. P. Mamede Counterfactual Impact Evaluation of Vocational Education in Portugal. (Co-author(s): D. Cruz, T. Fernandes)

G. Pellegrini Italian public guarantees to SME: the impact on regional growth. (Co-author(s): M. De Castris)

(SOL-14) Usage of geocoded micro data in the economic analysis

M. Dickson Spatial sampling methods with locational errors. (Co-author(s): D. Filipponi)

D. Giuliani Spatial Micro-Econometrics Models with Locational Errors. (Co-author(s): S. Cozzi, G. Espa)

F. Santi Three-Year Survival Probability of Italian Start-up Businesses in Health-care Industry: an Empirical Investigation through Logistic Multilevel Modelling. (Co-author(s): M. M. Dickson, D. Giuliani, D. Piacentino)

(SOL-15) Statistical models in functional data analysis

G. Adelfio Space-time FPCA Algorithm for clustering of multidimensional curves. (Co-author(s): F. Di Salvo, M. Chiodi)

C. Miller Functional data analysis approaches for satellite remote sensing applications. (Co-author(s): R. O’Donnell, M. Gong, M. Scott)

E. Romano Order statistics for spatially dependent functional data. (Co-author(s): A. Balzanella, R. Verde)

L. M. Sangalli [A penalized regression model for functional data with spatial dependence.](#) (Co-author(s): M. S. Bernardi, G. Mazza, J. O. Ramsay)

(SOL-16) Forecasting economic and financial time series

G. Goracci [Asymptotics and power of entropy based tests of dependence for categorical data.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Giannerini)

M. M. Pelagatti [Forecasting electricity load and price: a comparison of different approaches.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Lisi)

G. Storti [Flexible Realized GARCH Models.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Gerlach)

(SOL-17) Immigrations and integration in Italy

O. Casacchia [Minorities internal migration in Italy: an analysis based on gravity models.](#) (Co-author(s): C. Reynaud, S. Strozza, E. Tucci)

C. Conti [Growing generations and new models of integration.](#)

N. Tedesco [Measurement of segregation in the labour market. An alternative approach.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Salaris)

L. Terzera [Family behaviours among first generation migrants.](#) (Co-author(s): E. Barbiano di Belgiojoso)

(SOL-18) Open data, linked data and big data in public administration and official statistics

G. Di Bella [Linked Administrative Data in Official Statistics: a Positive Feedback for the Quality?.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Garofalo)

C. Martelli [Generating high quality administrative data: new technologies in a national statistical reuse perspective.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Calzaroni, A. Samaritani)

V. Santarcangelo [An innovative approach about the analysis of quality and efficiency in Italian law.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Buondonno, A. Romano, M. Giacalone, C. Cusatelli)

B. Squitieri [Prato municipality experience towards a high integration between administrative and statistical data.](#)

(SOL-19) Evaluation of prognostic biomarkers

F. Ambrogi [Combining Clinical and Omics data: hope or illusion?.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Boracchi)

L. Antolini [Graphical representations and summary indicators to assess the performance of risk predictors.](#) (Co-author(s): D. Bernasconi)

P. Chiodini [Multivariable prognostic model: external validation and model recalibration with application to non-metastatic renal cell carcinoma.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Cindolo)

(SOL-20) Models for studying the mobility of students

- S. Balia** [Modelling inter-regional patient mobility: evidence from the Italian NHS.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Brau, E. Marrocu)
- A. D'Agostino** [University mobility at enrollment: geographical disparities in Italy.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Ghellini, S. Longobardi)
- M. Enea** [From South to North? Mobility of Southern Italian students at the transition from the first to the second level university degree.](#)
- F. Giambona** [Measuring territory student-attractiveness in Italy. Longitudinal evidence.](#)

CONTRIBUTED SESSION (CON)

(CON-01) Bayesian statistics (1)

- F. Giummolè** [Reference priors based on composite likelihoods.](#) (Co-author(s): V. Mameli, L. Ventura)
- B. Nipoti** [On Bayesian nonparametric inference for discovery probabilities.](#) (Co-author(s): J. Arbel, S. Favaro, Y. W. Teh)
- R. Pappadà** [Relabelling in Bayesian mixture models by pivotal units.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Egidi, F. Pauli, N. Torelli)
- C. Scricciolo** [On Deconvolution of Dirichlet-Laplace Mixtures.](#)

(CON-02) Statistical modeling

- P. Faroughi** [A New Bivariate Regression Model for Count Data with Excess Zeros.](#) (Co-author(s): N. Ismail)
- B. Francis** [Dynamic latent class profiles in cross-sectional surveys: some preliminary results.](#) (Co-author(s): V. Hoti)
- P. M. Kroonenberg** [The use of deviance plots for non-nested model selection in loglinear models, structural equations, three-mode analysis.](#)
- A. Lucadamo** [Variable selection through Multinomial LASSO for PCMR.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Greco)
- O. Paccagnella** [Integrating CUB Models and Vignette Approaches.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Pavan, M. Iannario)

(CON-03) Demographics and social statistics (1)

- D. Bellani** [Gender egalitarianism, education and life-long singlehood: A multilevel analysis.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Esping-Andersen, L. Nedoluzhko)
- L. Colangelo** [Fear of Crime and Victimization among Sexual Harassed Women: Evidence from Italy.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Mancini)

S. De Cantis [A survival approach for the analysis of cruise passengers' behavior at the destination.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Ferrante, A. Parroco, N. Shoval)

A. Di Pino [Retirement of the Male Partner and the Housework Division in the Italian Couples: Estimation of the Causal Effects.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Campolo)

F. Laricca [Many women start, but few continue: determinants of breastfeeding in Italy.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Pinnelli)

(CON-04) Environmental statistics

F. Bono [Measuring sustainable economic development through a multidimensional Gini index.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Giacomarra, R. Giaimo)

C. Calculli [Modeling multi-site individual corals growth.](#) (Co-author(s): B. Cafarelli, D. Cocchi, E. Pignotti)

F. Di Salvo [GAMs and functional kriging for air quality data.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Plaia, M. Ruggieri)

F. Durante [The Kendall distribution and multivariate risks.](#)

(CON-05) Health statistics

E. di Bella [Dental care systems across Europe: the case of Switzerland.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Leporatti, I. Krejci, S. Ardu)

F. Gasperoni [Multi-state models for hospitalizations of heart failure patients in Trieste.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Ieva, G. Barbati)

F. Grossetti [Multi-state Approach to Administrative Data on Patients affected by Chronic Heart Failure.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Ieva, S. Scalvini, A. M. Paganoni)

G. Montanari [Evaluation of health care services through a latent Markov model with covariates.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Pandolfi)

(CON-06) Labor market statistics

A. Bianchi [Multifactor Partitioning: an analysis of employment and firm size.](#) (Co-author(s): S. Biffignandi)

G. Busetta [Ugly Betty looks for a job. Will she ever find it in Italy?.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Fiorillo)

G. Busetta [No country for foreigners: an analysis of hiring process in Italian labor market.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Campolo, D. Panarello)

F. Crippa [Know your audience. Towards a partnership between employers and university.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Zenga)

I. Vannini [Online Job Vacancies: a big data analysis.](#) (Co-author(s): D. Rotalone, C. Di Stefano, A. P. Paliotta, D. F. Iezzi)

(CON-07) Robust statistics

- F. Greselin** [Robust estimation of mixtures of skew-normal distributions.](#) (Co-author(s): L. García-Escudero, A. Mayo-Isacar, G. McLachlan)
- M. Musio** [Renyi's Scoring Rules.](#) (Co-author(s): A. F. Dawid)
- A. Paganoni** [Robust classification of multivariate functional data.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Ieva)
- G. C. Porzio** [A robust estimator for the mean direction of the von Mises-Fisher distribution.](#) (Co-author(s): T. Kirschstein, S. Liebscher, G. Pandolfo, G. Ragozini)
- F. Palumbo** [Robust Partial Possibilistic Regression Path Modeling.](#) (Co-author(s): R. Romano)

(CON-08) Sampling methods

- A. Ghiglietti** [Adaptive Randomly Reinforced Urn design and its asymptotic properties.](#)
- D. Marella** [PC algorithm from complex sample data.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Vicard)
- S. Missiroli** [Optimal Adaptive Group Sequential Procedure for Finite Populations in the Presence of a Cost Function.](#) (Co-author(s): E. Carfagna)
- E. Pelle** [The Rao regression-type estimator in ranked set sampling.](#) (Co-author(s): P. Perri)
- M. Ruggiero** [Modelling stationary varying-size populations via Polya sampling.](#) (Co-author(s): P. De Blasi, S. Walker)

(CON-09) Economic data analysis

- M. Brunetti** [Getting older and riskier: the effect of Medicare on household portfolio choices.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Angrisani, V. Atella)
- E. Ciavolino** [Modelling the Public Opinion on the European Economy with the HO-MIMIC Model.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Carpita)
- G. D'Epifanio** [Indexing the Worthiness of Social Agents. To norm index on conventional specifications.](#)
- G. Guagnano** [An econometric model for undeclared work.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Arezzo)
- M. Mussini** [A spatial shift-share decomposition of energy consumption variation.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Grossi)

(CON-10) Quantile methods

- M. Bernardi** [Bayesian inference for \$L_p\$ -quantile regression models.](#) (Co-author(s): V. Bignozzi, L. Petrella)
- V. Bignozzi** [On the \$L_p\$ -quantiles and the Student \$t\$ distribution.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Bernardi, L. Petrella)
- M. Marino** [M-quantile regression for multivariate longitudinal data.](#) (Co-author(s): M. Alfò, M. Ranalli, N. Salvati)

D. Vistocco [Comparing Prediction Intervals in Quantile and OLS Regression.](#) (Co-author(s): C. Davino)

(CON-11) Statistical algorithms

N. Loperfido [An Algorithm for Finding Projections with Extreme Kurtosis.](#) (Co-author(s): C. Franceschini)

L. Scrucca [Poisson change-point models estimated by Genetic Algorithms.](#)

A. Stamm [Maximum Likelihood Estimators of Brain White Matter Microstructure.](#) (Co-author(s): O. Commowick, S. Vantini, S. K. Warfield)

(CON-12) Statistics for medicine

G. Barbati [Competing risks between mortality and heart failure hospital re-admissions: a community-based investigation from the Trieste area.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Ieva, A. Scagnetto, G. Sinagra, A. Di Lenarda)

C. Brombin [Evaluating association between emotion recognition and Heart Rate Variability indices.](#) (Co-author(s): F. Cugnata, R. M. Martoni, M. Ferrario, C. Di Serio)

M. Ferrante [Socio-economic deprivation, territorial inequalities and mortality for cardiovascular diseases in Sicily.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Millito, A. Parroco)

M. Giacalone [The use of Permutation Tests on Large-Sized Datasets.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Alibrandi, A. Zirilli)

(CON-13) Statistics for the education system

G. Boscaino [Further considerations on a new indicator for higher education student performance.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Adelfio, V. Capursi)

C. Masci [Analysis of pupils' INVALSI achievements by means of bivariate multi-level models.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Paganoni, F. Ieva, T. Agasisti)

A. Valentini [Promoting statistical literacy to university students: a new approach adopted by Istat.](#) (Co-author(s): G. De Candia, M. Carbonara)

(CON-14) Testing procedures

E. Cascini [A Reliability Problem: Censored Tests.](#)

G. De Santis [Testing the Gamma-Gompertz-Makeham model.](#) (Co-author(s): G. Salinari)

M. M. Pelagatti [A nonparametric test of independence.](#)

A. Pini [Functional Data Analysis of Tongue Profiles.](#) (Co-author(s): L. Spreafico, S. Vantini, A. Vietti)

A. Vagheggin [On the asymptotic power of the statistical test under Response-Adaptive randomization.](#) (Co-author(s): A. Baldi Antognini, M. Zagoraiou)

(CON-15) Time series analysis

- C. Cappelli** [Robust Atheoretical Regression Tree to detect structural breaks in financial time series.](#) (Co-author(s): P. D'Urso, F. Di Iorio)
- P. Chirico** [Prediction intervals for heteroscedastic series by Holt-Winters methods.](#)
- M. Costa** [Inequality decomposition for financial variables evaluation.](#)
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(CON-16) Forecasting methods

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A Bayesian nonparametric approach to macroeconomic risk

Un approccio Bayesiano nonparametrico al rischio macroeconomico

Monica Billio and Roberto Casarin and Michele Costola and Michele Guindani

Abstract We apply a Bayesian nonparametric test for distributional changes in large panels of time series from macroeconomics. The test allows for detecting structural changes in the sequence of cross-sectional conditional distributions.

Abstract *Viene applicato a diversi panel di serie storiche economiche un test Bayesiano nonparametrico per il cambiamento distribuzionale. Il test consente di rilevare cambiamenti strutturali nella distribuzione condizionale dell'insieme di serie storiche.*

Key words: Bayesian nonparametric, Macroeconomic Risk, Time series.

1 Introduction

Our Bayesian approach to the estimation of distribution of the data rely on Pittman-Yor and Dirichlet process priors [6, 13, 17]. This type of approach is now widely used in statistics and econometrics due to the availability of efficient algorithms for posterior computations [5, 14, 19, 21, 12], including but not limited to applications in time series settings [9, 16, 20, 11, 7, 8, 2]. A related paper to our approach is [1] which considers the problem of estimating Shannon's entropy from discrete data, in cases where the number of possible bins is unknown or even countably infinite.

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They propose a mixture of Pitman-Yor processes and show that the resulting Pitman-Yor Mixture (PYM) entropy estimator is consistent for a large class of distributions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem of inferring the sequence of distribution from a sequence of cross sectional observations. Section ?? develops the sequential homogeneity test. Section ?? provides an empirical application to a large macroeconomic dataset. Finally, Section 4 concludes.

2 A test for distributional changes

Let $\{x_{it}\}_{i=1}^{n_t}$ be an i.i.d. sequence of observations, with $t = 1, \dots, T$ from the sequence of discrete distribution

$$p(x|\boldsymbol{\pi}_t) = \sum_{j=1}^m \pi_{jt} \mathbb{I}_{\{j\}}(x) \quad (1)$$

with $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \infty\}$, $\sum_{j=1}^m \pi_j = 1$, and $\mathbb{I}_A(x)$ is the indicator function, which takes value 1 if $x \in A$ and 0 otherwise. The likelihood of the data at time t is a product of multinomial distribution and can be written as

$$p(\mathbf{x}_t|\boldsymbol{\pi}_t) = \prod_{i=1}^{n_t} \prod_{j=1}^m \pi_{jt}^{\mathbb{I}_{\{j\}}(x_{it})} = \sum_{j=1}^m \pi_{jt}^{n_{jt}} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{1t}, \dots, x_{n_t t})$, and $n_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} \mathbb{I}_{\{i\}}(x_{jt})$ is the count for bin i .

Following a recent stream of literature (e.g., see, [9, 16, 20, 11, 7, 8, 2]) we propose a Bayesian nonparametric approach to density estimation. We consider a sequence of Poisson-Dirichlet processes (see [8, 2]), also known as Pitman-Yor processes (see [15]). Let $\boldsymbol{\pi}_t \sim PY(d, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ with stick-breaking representation

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\pi}_{it} &= v_{it} \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} (1 - v_{jt}) \\ v_{jt} &\sim Be(1 - d, \boldsymbol{\alpha} + jd) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The Dirichlet process prior, which has been recently used in some econometric applications, is a special case of the PY prior when $d = 0$.

Given the sample \mathbf{x}_t , with k_t the cardinality of $\{i = 1, 2, \dots | n_{it} > 0\}$, the number of non-empty bins, three quantities are usually of interest in econometric analysis. The first one is the posterior distribution of the multinomial probabilities. Under the assumption of the Pitman-Yor process prior the posterior distribution of $\boldsymbol{\pi}_t$, $G(\boldsymbol{\pi}_t|\mathbf{x}_t)$, is a mixture of a finite Dirichlet distribution and a Pitman-Yor process, that is

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}_t|\mathbf{x}_t \sim \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} p_{jt} \mathbb{I}_j(\boldsymbol{\pi}_{jt}) \quad (4)$$

where $(p_{1t}, \dots, p_{k_t+1}) \sim \mathcal{D}ir(n_{1t} - d, \dots, n_{k_t} - d, \alpha + dk_t)$ and $p_{jt} \sim PY(d, \alpha + dk_t)$, $j > k_t + 1$. See [10], Corollary 1.

In order to build an homogeneity test let us define $\{x_{it}\}_{i=1}^{n_t}$ and $\{x_{is}\}_{i=1}^{n_s}$, two samples from $p(x|\pi_t)$ and $p(y|\pi_s)$. Consider the null hypothesis,

$$H_0 : p(x|\pi_t) \approx p(y|\pi_s) \text{ with } \pi_t \neq \pi_s, \quad (5)$$

where we denote with p_0 the prior probability that $p(x|\pi_t) \sim p(y|\pi_s)$ and with $PY(\alpha_1, d_1)$ the prior process under the alternative, then the posterior distribution is

$$\begin{aligned} p(H_0|\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s) &= \left(1 + \frac{1-p_0}{p_0} \frac{m_1(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s)}{f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s|H_0)}\right)^{-1} \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1-p_0}{p_0} \frac{1}{B_{01}^\pi(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s)}\right)^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$B_{01}^\pi(x, y) = \frac{p(\mathbf{x}_t|d, \alpha)p(\mathbf{x}_s|\tilde{d}, \tilde{\alpha})}{p(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s|d_1, \alpha_1)}.$$

The Bayes factor can be related to the entropy of the frequencies thanks to the entropy-based approximation of the evidence as state in the following.

Proposition 1

$$\log B_{01}^\pi(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_s) \approx n_t D(\tilde{\pi}_t \| \tilde{\pi}_{t,s}) + n_s D(\tilde{\pi}_s \| \tilde{\pi}_{t,s}) + (\xi_{t,s} - \xi_t - \xi_s) \quad (7)$$

where

$$D(p|q) = \sum_k p_k \log \frac{p_k}{q_k}.$$

is the KullbackLeibler divergence of q from p , $\tilde{\pi}_r$ has elements $\tilde{\pi}_{jr} = n_{jr}/n_r$, $j = 1, \dots, k_r$, $r = t, s$ and $\tilde{\pi}_{t,s}$ has elements $\tilde{\pi}_{j,t,s} = n_{j,t,s}/n_{t,s}$, $j = 1, \dots, k_{t,s}$.

Proof. See [3].

3 Macroeconomic risk

The changes in the cross section of macroeconomic variables have been investigated by many parties. [4] proposed a joint testing procedure, based on the predictive density of the data, for identifying convergence clubs in income per capita of the OECD countries. Recently, [18] studied the cross section of a large set of macroeconomic series in order to detect the turning point the US business cycle. We apply our homogeneity test to the cross section of the [18] series and obtain an effective indicator (blue line in Fig. 3) of changes in the level of economic activity. The indicators takes

Fig. 1 Sequential Bayes factor (red line), structural break indicator (blue line) and recession periods following the NBER dating of the cycle (grey bars). The structural break indicator takes value one if there is evidence of changes in the cross-sectional distribution of the macroeconomic series.

value one if there is evidence of changes in the cross-sectional distribution. A comparison with the NBER cycle (gray bars) suggest that our indicator is able to capture the turning points of the US business cycle.

4 Conclusion

In this note we successfully apply a Bayesian nonparametric test for distributional changes for measuring changes in the level of macroeconomic risk and detecting the turning points in the US business cycle.

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